

STUDYING THE PHOSPHATE-MOBILIZING ABILITY OF RHIZOBACTERIA OF THE GENUS PANTOEA

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Phosphorus is one of the main nutrients that provides a beneficial effect on the growth and development of plants, acceleration of the formation of reproductive organs and plant maturation, the formation of high and sustainable crop yields with favorable quality of marketable products [1, 3].

The main problem with phosphorus in soil is its rapid fixation and the efficiency of phosphorus solubilization rarely exceeds 10–20%. The fixed forms of phosphorus in acidic soils are aluminum and iron phosphates, and in neutral and alkaline soils they are calcium phosphates [5]. One of the promising directions for improving the phosphorus nutrition of plants is the use of indigenous phosphate-mobilizing microorganisms (bacteria, actinomycetes, fungi), which ensure the biological mobilization of hard-to-reach soil phosphates, as well as the activation of low-grade phosphorites [2].

Strains from the bacterial genera *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Rhizobium*, *Pantoea* and *Enterobacter* are strong phosphate-mobilizing bacteria. Representatives of the genus *Pantoea* are associated with a wide range of host plants: bacteria are able to colonize plant roots, leaves and stems, can provide benefits through the biosynthesis of the phytohormone indolylacetic acid (IAA), mobilize soil phosphates and fix nitrogen [4].

In this context, the purpose of our work is to study the phosphate mobilization properties of strains of rhizobacteria belonging to the genus *Pantoea*.

The object of the study were 2 strains of wheat rhizobacteria: *Pantoea* agglomerans 1P and *Pantoea* agglomerans 6P.

At the first stage of the research, a qualitative test was carried out for the acid-forming ability of *P. agglomerans* 1P and *P. agglomerans* 6P cultures on Pikovskaya medium with an indicator. Both rhizobacteria turned out to be active acid-formers, which gave 90% acid formation already on the 1st day of the experiment, and on the 2nd day of the experiment the acid formation was 100%.

When *P. agglomerans* 1R and *P. agglomerans* 6R cultures were grown in agar medium containing $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, it was observed that they strongly dissolved $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in the agar medium and formed a clear circle from 15 mm to 40 mm.

In the next series of experiments, in order to confirm the ability to form acids by a quantitative test, the total amount of titratable acids was determined in relation to 100 g of alkali. The results obtained confirmed the data of the qualitative acid formation test. *P. agglomerans* 1P most actively secreted acids relative to *P. agglomerans* 6P, the total acidity already on the first day of the experiment ranged from 19.2 ± 0.21 ml/100 mM NaOH, by the end of the experiment on the 10th day it was 22.6 ± 0.23 ml/100 mM NaOH.

Next, we studied the mobilization of P_2O_5 from $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ by cultures of wheat rhizobacteria *P. agglomerans* 1P and *P. agglomerans* 6P on a liquid medium. Mobilization of P_2O_5 from $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ added to peptone liquid nutrient medium by rhizobacteria was studied in dynamics (2, 4, 8 days). As a result of the conducted research, it was observed that $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ added to liquid nutrient medium with peptone was mobilized under the influence of organic acids released by *P. agglomerans* 1P and *P. agglomerans* 6P. It was found that rhizobacterial cultures decompose $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ to P_2O_5 most actively on the 4th day of the experiment.

It was observed that P_2O_5 from $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in liquid nutrient medium of *P. agglomerans* 1R was 5.7 mg P_2O_5 /100 ml on the 2nd day of the experiment, and 21.0 mg P_2O_5 /100 ml on the 4th day, respectively. *P. agglomerans* 6R culture on the 4th day of the experiment, the rate of degradation of P_2O_5 from $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ was 17.0 mg P_2O_5 /100 ml. By the 8th day of the experiment, it was observed that the studied cultures decreased the degradation of $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$. It was observed that rhizobacteria reduced the alkaline pH of the nutrient medium to acidic medium (pH 4.1-3.8). The optical density of *P. agglomerans* 1R and *P. agglomerans* 6R cultures (OZ590) was 1.5-2.1 on the 4th day of the experiment.

Thus, as a result of studying the phosphate mobilization properties of *P. agglomerans* 1P and *P. agglomerans* 6P rhizobacterial cultures, it was found that these cultures produce high organic acids and exhibit high activity in breaking down $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$. As a result of the conducted research, wheat rhizobacteria strains *P. agglomerans* 1P and *P. agglomerans* 6P can improve phosphorus nutrition of plants due to the decomposition of hard-to-assimilate $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ to P_2O_5 under the influence of organic acids.

REFERENCES

1. Bosak V. N. Optimization of plant nutrition / V. N. Bosak. - Saarbrücken: Lambert Academic Publishing, 2012. -203 p.
2. Belyasova N.A., Ignatovets O.S., Sergievich D.S., Minakovsky A.F., Bosak V.N. Isolation and characteristics of soil phosphate-mobilizing microorganisms // Journal Bulletin of the Belarusian State Agricultural Academy. 2018. No. 2. P. 93-97.
3. Carstensen, A., Herdean, A., Schmidt, S. B., Sharma, A., Spetea, C., Pribil, M., et al. (2018). The impacts of phosphorus deficiency on the photosynthetic electron transport chain. *Plant Physiol.* 177, 271–284. doi: 10.1104/pp.17.01624.
4. De Maayer P., Chan W.Y., Rezzonico F., Bühlmann A., Venter S.N., Blom J., Goesmann A., Frey J.E., Smits THM., Duffy B., Coutinho T.A. (2012) Complete genome sequence of clinical isolate *Pantoea ananatis* LMG 5342. *Journal of Bacteriology* 194(6): 1615-1616.
5. Kuhad R.K., Singh S., Lata, Singh A. Phosphate-Solubilizing Microorganisms. In: Singh A. et al., editors. *Bioaugmentation, Biostimulation and Biocontrol, Soil Biology* 28, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg; 2011.